

IT TECHNOLOGIES, DISTANCE LEARNING, ELECTRONIC DIGITAL IN
TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

¹Mansurova Zarifa Olimjonovna, ²Ilxomova Intizor Nurali qizi

¹Teacher of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages, ²Samarkand state institute of
foreign languages

¹zarishmansurova@gmail.com, ²Intizorrajabova32@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10816657>

Abstract. In the article, the teaching methodology, especially the role of IT technologies in the teaching of foreign languages and its useful aspects are deeply studied. The discussion includes the role of distance education and its importance and methods within the framework of foreign language teaching and integrates the ideas of different teaching methodologies. It emphasizes the importance of electronic digital education and its interdisciplinary nature. Conclusion the words provide a comprehensive overview of the topic, highlighting the contribution of IT technologies to distance learning and learning methods.

Keyword: distance learning, IT, teaching foreign languages, electronic digital, educational form, IT technologies and teaching method.

Annotatsiya. Xorijiy tillarni o'qitishda IT texnologiyalar, masofaviy talim, elektron raqamli ta'lim. Maqolada o'qitish metodikasi, xususan, xorijiy tillarni o'qitishda IT texnologiyalarning tutgan o'rni, uning foydali tomonlari chuqur o'rganilgan munozara masofaviy ta'limning rolini va chetillarni o'qitish doirasida uning ahamiyati va usullarini o'z ichiga oladi va turli o'qitish metodikalarining g'oyalarini birlashtiradi. Elektron raqamli ta'limning qay darajada muhimligi va uning fanlararo xususiyatini ta'kidlaydi. Yakuniy so'zlar IT texnologiyalar, masofaviy ta'lim va elektron raqamli ta'lim usullarining hissasini ta'kidlab, mavzuni har tomonlama ko'rib chiqishga yordam beradi.

Kalitso'zlar: masofaviy ta'lim, IT, chetillarni o'qitish, elektron raqamli ta'lim, o'quv jarayoni, IT texnologiyalar va o'qitish metodikasi.

Аннотация. ИТ технологии, дистанционное обучение, электронное в преподавание иностранных языков. В статье глубоко изучена методика преподавания ИТ-технологии, дистанционное обучение, электронное цифровое обучение в преподавании иностранных языков.

В статье глубоко изучена методика преподавания, особенности роли ИТ-технологий в преподавании иностранных языков, а также ее полезные аспекты. Обсуждение включает в себя роль дистанционного образования, его значение и методы в рамках преподавания иностранного языка, интегрирует идеи различных методик обучения, подчеркивает важность электронного цифрового образования и его междисциплинарный характер. Заключение. Слова дают всесторонний обзор эта тема, подчеркивающая вклад ИТ-технологий в методы дистанционного обучения и электронного обучения.

Ключевые слова: дистанционное образование, ИТ, обучение иностранным языкам, электронное цифровое образование, учебный процесс, ИТ-технологии, методика обучения.

Introduction

Modern conditions require not only the use of new technologies in teaching foreign languages, but also changes in the teaching methodology from the teacher to introduce the latest innovative technologies in the process of learning foreign languages. Higher educational institutions preferred to use active methods of teaching aimed at forming students' independence

and flexibility. Innovative technologies are the most necessary source of educational activities that develop students' creative abilities, skills and other mental characteristics. The internet can provide invaluable help to students in chat language learning. Access to the Internet helps to become fluent in a foreign language. The Internet as a means of information transfer is especially relevant for independent work of young people after school. Online students learn independently the benefits of working with large amounts of data, analyzing data, seeing problems, and finding solutions. In fact, the role of modern pedagogical technologies and information communication tools is very important in improving the quality and effectiveness of education, in the purposeful organization of lessons in the form of questions that interest students and young people. The scope of their application is expanding day by day, and technical tools are becoming an integral part of the educational process. Young people should be able to use foreign languages and computer technologies at a professional level. In addition, it has been proven that every rule, every word, every concept unit taught in the teaching of foreign languages with the help of IT technologies is better stored in the student's memory. makes teaching foreign languages through computers one of the most effective methods. Introducing IT technologies and ensuring that teaching methods meet the requirements of the times are the main tasks of pedagogues and scientists that cannot be delayed.

Today, digital technologies are actively used in all spheres of life. The economy, banking services, sectors, as well as the educational process, are rapidly developing. He is forming the opinion that it is possible to solve. The use of digital technologies in education facilitates the learning process of students, provides them with opportunities to create experiences and organize the educational process. There are a number of positive outcomes that can be achieved through the use of digital technologies in education. In particular,

1. digital technologies allow students to create experiences in their learning process.
2. It allows young people to express their personal thoughts, collaborate with other students, create new ideas and plans, and learn in the learning process. allows you to gain experience in the process.
3. In addition, digital technologies provide many opportunities to structure the learning process and provide students with opportunities that match their learning methods.
4. Most importantly, digital technologies help to develop the creativity of students and teachers.

The modern era encourages us to use tools like zoom, podcasts, etc. more innovatively. This contributes to a more independent way of learning and makes it more interactive. Technological innovations help to effectively organize group and independent work in seminars and lead to the improvement of practical skills and competencies of pupils and students, while developing the language learning process of students and increasing their interest in languages.

The distance education system is software for organizing distance education, additional support for the educational process, electronic document circulation, creating electronic educational material, managing management and evaluating progress within the subject being studied, as well as providing advice. Distance education involves the active use of Internet technologies that allow teaching when the teacher and student are far from each other. Now, the possibilities of the Internet or local computer networks are used for this. is the most suitable form of education. Distance education systems also allow preparing schoolchildren, students, and workers for the workplace. The use of distance education is especially effective in teaching a foreign language. they are attending tutors in order to get a certificate, whereas online foreign

language teaching classes are developing day by day, and in these classes, highly qualified teachers are directed, and many young people prefer online distance learning classes and achieve a good level of proficiency. This is also clear evidence of the rapid development of the distance education system. Indeed, learning and teaching a foreign language using distance learning is one of the most effective, useful and affordable methods.

Conclusion.

In short, digital educational resources and technologies make the educational process more convenient, increase student motivation, and help strengthen self-directed learning. These methods and opportunities are relevant in the development of the educational process. Also, digital technologies increase the cooperation between students and the scope of students' compatibility was closely related to PC-based exercises and practice activities aimed at supporting learning. This perspective has been replaced by a new approach to technology in foreign language teaching, and mass media has become an important tool for global interaction and global literacy.

REFERENCE.

1. Barkamolavlod O'zbekiston taraqqiyotining poydevori. -T.: "Sharq" nashriyoti-matbaa konserni, 1997. -56.
2. Беспалко В.П. Слагаемые педагогической технологии. -М.: «Педагогика», 1989. 192 May 12-13 Samarkand branch of Tashkent State Agrarian University Theoretical and practical foundations of introducing smart agriculture in Uzbekistan
3. O'zbekistonda aqlli qishloq xojaligini joriy etishning nazariy va amaliy asoslari
4. Кларин М.В. Педагогическая технология в учебном процессе. Анализ зарубежного опыта. -М.: «Знание», 1989-80 с. o'ldoshev J.G.,. Yangi pedagogik texnologiyayo'nalishlari, muammolari, yecimlari //Xalqta'limi, 1999, № 4. B.4-11.
5. Sayidaxmedov N. Yangi pedagogik texnologiyaning mohiyati. Xalqta'limi, 1999,
6. N.N. Azizxo'jaeva. Pedagogik texnologiyavapedagogik mahorat. T. Nizomiy nomidagi TDPU. 2003 y. -174 b.